

Unveiling Bacterial Diversity in the Holdfast and Rhizoidal Regions of *Sargassum wightii* and *Halimeda macroloba*

Nazeer Ahamed Sathakkathulla¹, Vinothkumar Suruli Palanichamy²,
Venkateshan Narayanan², Samundeswari Loganathan³, Sreenathkumar Chinnadurai³,
Kalaivani Devarajan⁴, Sivakumar Saroja Ramasubbu^{5*}

1 Department of Molecular and Cell Biology, Greensmed Labs, Thoraipakkam,
Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

2 Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Arulmigu Kalasalingam College of Pharmacy
(Affiliated to The TN Dr MGR Medical University, Chennai), Krishnankoil, Virudhunagar,
Tamil Nadu, India

3 PG & Research Department of Botany, Thiru A. Govindasamy Govt. Arts College,
Tindivanam, Tamil Nadu, India

(Affiliated to Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, Tamil Nadu)

4 Department of Biotechnology, Sri Ramachandra Institute of Higher Education and
Research, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

5 Department of Botany, Bharathidasan University, Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India

*Corresponding author

Dr.Sivakumar

Received: Nov 04, 2025

Accepted: Nov 30, 2025

Published: Dec 03, 2025

1. Abstract

Bacteria associated with marine macroalgae like *Sargassum wightii* and *Halimeda macroloba* play key roles in promoting host growth, producing bioactive compounds, and enhancing stress tolerance, making them promising candidates for use as microbial biofertilizers. The study focuses on the isolation and characterization of bacterial strains from the holdfast region of *Sargassum wightii* and rhizoidal region of *Halimeda macroloba*, collected from the coastal area of Thonithurai in the Mandapam region of Rameswaram, Tamil Nadu. The isolates were initially characterized using morphological traits, Gram staining, and biochemical assays. Two strains from *Sargassum wightii* showing notable biochemical characteristics were selected for species level identification through 16S rRNA gene sequencing and BLAST analysis. *Bacillus*

subtilis (isolate IB.6a.1) exhibited 95% sequence similarity with reference strains. *Halobacillus dabanensis* showed 97.8-99.4% similarity with other *Halobacillus* species, and phylogenetic analysis further confirmed the classification of both isolates within their respective genera. Similarly, from the rhizoidal region of *Halimeda macroloba*, two morphologically and biochemically distinct bacterial strains were identified as *Bacillus mycooides* and *Halobacillus blutaparonensis*, with 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity ranging from 97.8–99.4% to their respective reference strains, confirming their taxonomic identity through BLAST and phylogenetic analysis. The results indicate that bacteria associated with seaweeds may serve as valuable producers of bioactive metabolites. Further studies are warranted to purify and characterize the active metabolites and evaluate their use in biofertilizer development and other applications in sustainable marine biotechnology.

Keywords: *Sargassum wightii*, *Halimeda macroloba*, 16S rRNA gene sequencing

2. Graphical Abstract

Abbreviations & Symbols

16S rRNA - 16S ribosomal ribonucleic acid

BLAST - Basic Local Alignment Search Tool

bp - Base pairs

DNA - Deoxyribonucleic acid

DMSP - Dimethylsulfoniopropionate

IAA	- Indole-3-Acetic Acid
MR	- Methyl Red
NA	- Nutrient Agar
PCR	- Polymerase Chain Reaction
PGPB	- Plant Growth-Promoting Bacteria
VP	- Voges–Proskauer
rpm	- Revolutions per minute
°C	- Degrees Celsius
μL	- Microliters

3. Introduction

Marine macroalgae or seaweeds, are diverse photosynthetic organisms that play a crucial ecological role in coastal environments. Unlike higher plants, macroalgae lack true roots, stems, and leaves, and instead possess a thallus that facilitates nutrient absorption directly from seawater [1]. Among them, brown macroalgae such as *Sargassum wightii* and *Halimeda macroloba* are particularly significant due to their unique biochemical composition, ecological roles, and biotechnological potential. *S. wightii*, a member of the Sargassaceae family under the order Fucales, is commonly found along tropical and temperate coasts in Asia, particularly in India, where it thrives in nearshore marine environments and supports various marine life [2].

The ecological success and physiological health of seaweeds like *S. wightii* are strongly influenced by their associated microbial communities. Bacterial communities, particularly those on the holdfast region of seaweeds, establish stable associations with their host, collectively forming a holobiont, an ecologically interconnected system composed of seaweed and its associated microbiota [3], [4]. These bacteria contribute significantly to seaweed development by aiding nutrient absorption, promoting morphological changes, and synthesizing antimicrobial and antioxidant substances that defend the host against pathogens

and surface colonization of organisms [5], [6]. Additionally, secondary metabolites like terpenoids and dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP), produced by microbes, are known to enhance seaweed resistance by improving their tolerance to oxidative stress and abiotic stress [6], [7], [8].

Sargassum wightii contains a variety of bioactive compounds such as sulfated polysaccharides (e.g., fucoidans), flavonoids, terpenoids, and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), which are associated with a range of pharmacological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticoagulant, and anti-neoplastic effects [1], [2], [9]. Recent studies have revealed its potential in managing oxidative stress-related complications such as cardiovascular disorders and diabetes. The presence of omega-3, -6, and -9 fatty acids further enhances the nutritional and therapeutic value of *Sargassum wightii*, especially in modulating inflammation and oxidative stress [1].

Halimeda macroloba is a calcified green seaweed commonly found in coral reef ecosystems, contributing significantly to calcium carbonate deposition and habitat structuring [10]. It thrives in complex marine conditions including high salinity, elevated heavy metal concentrations, and biotic stress, suggesting a robust physiological makeup and possibly symbiotic microbial adaptations. Despite its ecological prominence, the bioactive potential of *H. macroloba* remains underexplored. Existing studies have revealed its antioxidant, antibacterial, and cytotoxic properties, and identified its secondary metabolites as effective against various human and aquatic pathogens [11]. Beyond its therapeutic potential, *H. macroloba* like other green seaweeds is known to contribute to marine ecosystem health through its association with beneficial epiphytic microbes that aid in nutrient cycling and host defense [12]. *Halimeda* species have been explored as sustainable sources of plant biostimulants and organic fertilizers, offering an environmentally friendly alternative to synthetic agrochemicals [13]. These attributes make *H. macroloba* a promising candidate for further investigation in marine microbiology, particularly regarding its associated bacterial communities and their potential applications in biotechnology.

Seaweed also produce a broad range of structurally novel metabolites, including flavonoids, alkaloids, and prebiotic polysaccharides such as inulin and oligosaccharides, which exhibit significant antibacterial activity and gut microbiome modulation potential in humans [14]. With the rise of antimicrobial resistance, macroalgae derived bioactives have gained attention in

pharmaceutical research for offering alternative therapeutic mechanisms distinct from conventional synthetic drugs [2]. Recent studies suggest that brown macroalgae support a wide variety of epiphytic bacterial genera, including *Bacillus*, *Pseudoalteromonas*, *Psychrobacter*, *Vibrio*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Halomonas* [2], [14]. These bacteria are known to contribute to nitrogen fixation, morphogenesis, and the secretion of growth-promoting and antimicrobial metabolites. Various *Bacillus* species linked to marine algae are known to synthesize lipopeptides, biosurfactants, and enzymes with the ability to inhibit surface colonization organisms and pathogenic microbes [15], [16]. Some studies also highlight their role in zoospore induction and algal tissue development, although the exact molecular mechanisms are still being elucidated [17], [18], [19]. These functional traits not only support algal survival in dynamic marine environments but also make such bacteria promising candidates for applications in biotechnology. While the ecological significance of seaweed-associated microbial communities has been widely acknowledged, limited studies have focused on the specific identification and functional characterization of bacteria residing in the holdfast region of *S. wightii* and rhizoidal region of *H. macroloba*. Understanding the microbial diversity in this niche is essential for exploring their potential as biofertilizers, yet the metabolic traits and species composition of these bacteria remain largely unexamined. Hence, the current work focuses on the isolation, identification and biochemical characterization of the bacteria that were found to be localized at the holdfast region of *S. wightii* and rhizoidal region of *H. macroloba*.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1 Collection of Seaweed

Seaweed samples were collected from the coastal area of Thoni Thurai, near the Pamban Bridge (9.369763°N, 78.830838°E), in the Mandapam region of Rameswaram, Tamil Nadu, India. The brown macroalgae *Sargassum wightii* and the green macroalgae *Halimeda macroloba* were manually collected during low tide at the chart datum level. Species identification was carried out by Dr. S.R. Shivakumar, Department of Botany, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu. The samples were rinsed with seawater, stored in plastic containers containing fresh water, and transported to the laboratory for further analysis [20].

4.2 Isolation of Bacteria

Seaweed specimens were initially rinsed under running water and transferred to sterile Petri dishes. The holdfast portion of *S. wightii* and rhizoidal region of *H. macroloba* was carefully excised using a sterile surgical blade and further cleaned by sequential rinsing with sterile seawater and distilled water to eliminate surface contaminants [21]. To sterilize the surface, the samples were immersed in 0.1% mercuric chloride for three minutes, followed by a five-minute treatment with 70% ethanol. Sterile holdfast and rhizoidal fragments were aseptically sectioned and inoculated onto nutrient agar medium supplemented with 3.2% NaCl. The medium was prepared by dissolving 28 g of nutrient agar in 1 L of distilled water, followed by autoclaving at 121 °C for 15 minutes [22], [23]. The prepared plates were then incubated at room temperature for 48 hours. Distinct colonies were then selected and purified through quadrant streaking to obtain isolated bacterial strains [24].

4.3 Morphological Identification

4.3.1 Gram Staining

To distinguish bacterial cells based on differences in their cell wall composition, a loopful of culture was placed in a drop of distilled water on a clean glass slide, spread into a thin smear, and heat-fixed. The prepared smear was initially stained with crystal violet for one minute, followed by a gentle rinse with distilled water. Gram's iodine was then applied for 30 seconds to allow the formation of the crystal violet–iodine complex. After decolorization with ethanol, the slide was rinsed once more and finally counterstained with safranin for two minutes. Following a final wash, the slide was air-dried and examined under a light microscope using 100X oil immersion. Gram-positive bacteria appear purple due to their thick peptidoglycan layer, which retains the primary stain, while Gram-negative bacteria were observed as pink after taking up the counterstain [21], [25], [26].

4.3.2 Motility Test (Hanging Drop Technique)

To assess bacterial motility, a drop of the culture broth was placed onto the center of a sterile coverslip. This coverslip was then gently inverted over the concavity of a cavity slide to form a hanging drop. The setup was examined under a light microscope, and motility was identified by observing the directional movement of bacterial cells, suggesting active flagellar function [27].

4.4 Biochemical Tests

4.4.1 Indole Test

To assess indole production, a biochemical test involving the enzymatic breakdown of tryptophan by tryptophanase was conducted. A loopful of the bacterial culture was inoculated into 5 mL of sterile tryptone water broth and incubated at 37 °C for 48 hours. Following incubation, several drops of Kovac's reagent were added to the tube. The development of a cherry-red layer at the junction of the reagent and the broth indicated a positive indole test [21], [28], [29].

4.4.2 Methyl Red Test

To evaluate mixed acid fermentation, a small amount of bacterial culture was inoculated into 2 mL of sterile MR-VP broth and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. After incubation, three to four drops of methyl red indicator were added to the broth. The development of a red coloration confirms the production of stable acids from glucose fermentation [23], [26].

4.4.3 Voges Proskauer Test

To detect the production of acetoin (a precursor of 2,3-butanediol), the bacterial culture was inoculated into 5 mL of sterile MR-VP broth and incubated at 37 °C for 24 to 48 hours. After incubation, 15 drops of Barritt's reagent A were added, followed by 5 drops of Barritt's reagent B. The appearance of a red coloration confirms the presence of acetoin [30], [31].

4.4.4 Citrate Utilization Test

To evaluate citrate utilization as the sole carbon source, 5 mL of sterile molten Simmon's citrate agar was poured into a test tube to prepare a slant. After solidification, the slant was streaked with a loopful of bacterial culture and incubated. A change in color from green to Prussian blue signified a positive result, resulting from a pH rise associated with citrate utilization. This shift was detected by the bromothymol blue indicator present in the medium [25], [32].

4.4.5 Oxidase Test

To assess the presence of the cytochrome c oxidase enzyme, 1 mL of oxidase reagent (N,N,N',N'-tetramethyl-p-phenylenediamine) was added to 5 mL of the bacterial culture broth. The mixture was then monitored for any color change. A positive result was indicated by the rapid development of a dark blue or purple coloration, signifying oxidation of the reagent by cytochrome c oxidase produced by the organism [24].

4.4.6 Catalase Test

To detect catalase activity, a drop of 3% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was added to a drop of bacterial culture placed on a clean glass slide. The rapid appearance of gas bubbles indicated the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide into water and oxygen, confirming the presence of catalase enzyme in the sample [15], [33].

4.5 Molecular Identification

4.5.1 Genomic DNA Extraction

Genomic DNA was isolated from bacterial cultures using the EXposure Microbial DNA Isolation Kit (Bogar Bio Bee Stores Pvt. Ltd.) in accordance with the manufacturer's protocol, incorporating minor modifications [21], [24]. One to three well-isolated colonies were suspended in 500 µL of lysis buffer within a 2 mL microcentrifuge tube and disrupted by repeated pipetting. Following lysis, 500 µL of neutralization buffer and 4 µL of RNase were added. The mixture was vortexed and incubated at 65 °C for 30 minutes, with gentle inversion to reduce DNA shearing. The tubes were then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The resulting supernatant was transferred to a new tube, combined with 600 µL of binding buffer, incubated at room temperature for 5 minutes, and applied to a spin column fitted in a 2 mL collection tube. After centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 2 minutes, the process was repeated with the remaining lysate. The column was washed sequentially with 500 µL of Washing Buffer I and Washing Buffer II, each followed by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 2 minutes, and then subjected to a final dry spin for 5 minutes. Subsequently, the spin column was placed into a sterile 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube, and 100 µL of elution buffer was added directly to the membrane. After a 2-minute incubation at room temperature, DNA was eluted by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 2 minutes. The extracted DNA was then quantified using either 1% agarose gel electrophoresis or a Qubit Fluorometer 3.0 [17].

4.5.2 PCR

The 16S rRNA gene was amplified using polymerase chain reaction (PCR) in a 25 µL reaction volume. The reaction mixture included 12 µL of 2X Taq Master Mix, which contained Taq DNA polymerase, 0.4 mM dNTPs, 3.2 mM MgCl₂, and 0.02% bromophenol blue, along with 1.5 µL each of forward and reverse primers (as listed in Table 1), 5 µL of nuclease-free water, and 5 µL of genomic DNA template. The amplification was performed under thermal cycling conditions described in Table 2, following protocols adapted from [34], [35]. Post

amplification, the amplified products were purified using the Montage PCR Clean-up Kit (Millipore) to remove residual primers and unincorporated nucleotides.

Table : 1 Primer sequences used for 16S rRNA gene amplification

Primer Name	Sequence Details	Number of Base
27F	5'A GAG TTT GAT CTG GCT CAG 3'	20
1492R	5'TACGGTACCTTGTTACGACTT3'	20

Table:2 Stages of PCR

Stages	Temperature (°C)	Time (min/sec)
Initial Denaturation	95°C	2min
Denaturation	95°C	30sec
Annealing	50°C	30sec
Extension	72°C	2min
Final extension	72°C	10min
Hold	4°C	∞

4.5.3 16S rRNA Sequencing

Each DNA template was treated with single-pass sequencing using universal primers targeting the 16S rRNA gene. To remove unincorporated terminators, fluorescently labeled fragments were purified through ethanol precipitation, following the protocol described by [35]. The resulting clean products were resuspended in distilled water and analyzed by capillary electrophoresis using an ABI 3730xl DNA sequencer (Applied Biosystems).

4.5.4 Phylogenetic Analysis

The 16S rRNA gene sequence obtained from the isolate was subjected to a similarity search using the NCBI BLASTn tool to identify closely related sequences [36]. The top BLAST hits were retrieved, and multiple sequence alignment was performed using MUSCLE v3.7 [25]. To improve the quality of the alignment, poorly aligned and highly divergent regions were removed using Gblocks v0.91b, which reduces background noise and improves phylogenetic resolution. Phylogenetic tree construction was carried out using PhyML v3.0 with the

approximate likelihood-ratio test (aLRT) and the HKY85 nucleotide substitution model. PhyML has been demonstrated to provide both high accuracy and computational efficiency compared to other tree-building methods [37]. The resulting phylogenetic tree was visualized using TreeDyn v198.3.

5. Results

5.1 Isolation of Bacteria

Bacterial strains were successfully isolated from two different macroalgae, the holdfast region of *Sargassum wightii* and the rhizoidal region of *Halimeda macroloba*. From *S. wightii*, two prominent strains were identified based on colony morphology, pigmentation, and growth patterns, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Halobacillus dabanensis*. *B. subtilis* formed smooth, pink-colored colonies (Fig 1a), while *H. dabanensis* exhibited yellowish-orange colonies with a slightly dry texture (Fig 1b). Both isolates showed motility and were purified by repeated subculturing using the streak plate method. Similarly, from *H. macroloba*, two morphologically distinct strains, *Bacillus mycoides* and *Halobacillus blutaparonsis* were isolated. *B. mycoides* formed large, opaque colonies with rhizoidal margins, consistent with its filamentous growth (Fig 2a), while *H. blutaparonsis* produced smooth, cream-colored colonies with a circular shape (Fig 2b).

Figure 1: Streak plate isolation of bacterial strains from *Sargassum wightii* holdfast on nutrient agar supplemented with 3.2% NaCl (a) Smooth pink colonies of *Bacillus subtilis* (b) Yellowish-orange, dry-textured colonies of *Halobacillus dabanensis*

Figure 2: Streak plate isolation of bacterial strains from rhizoidal region of *Halimeda macroloba* on nutrient agar (a) Large, opaque colonies of *Bacillus mycoides* (b) Smooth, cream-colored colonies with a circular shape of *Halobacillus blutaparonensis*

5.2 Molecular Characterization

The isolate IB.6a.1 demonstrated 95% sequence similarity to reference strains of *Bacillus subtilis* (Fig. 3a). Similarly, BLAST analysis at NCBI revealed that the second *Sargassum*-derived isolate aligned with *Halobacillus dabanensis*, showing 97.8% to 99.4% sequence similarity with related species (Fig. 3b). Phylogenetic analysis based on 16S rRNA gene sequences further supported the accurate taxonomic placement of both isolates within their respective genera.

Similarly, isolates obtained from the rhizoidal region of *Halimeda macroloba* were identified as *Bacillus mycoides* and *Halobacillus blutaparonensis*. These strains also showed high similarity (97.8–99.4%) to their corresponding type strains in BLAST analysis, and their classification was corroborated by phylogenetic tree construction (Figs. 3c & 3d). All four isolates were confirmed as Gram-positive, spore-forming bacteria belonging to the phylum *Firmicutes*, consistent with their observed morphological and biochemical characteristics.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 3 : Phylogenetic analysis of bacterial isolates based on 16S rRNA gene sequences

(a) *Bacillus subtilis* isolate showed 95% similarity and clustered with other known *B. subtilis* strains, such as *B. haikouensis* and *B. oryzaecorticis*, confirming its classification within the *Bacillus subtilis* group (b) *Halobacillus dabanensis* isolate displayed 97.8–99.4% sequence similarity and formed a close clade with *H. dabanensis*, *H. trueperi*, and *H. profundi*, affirming its phylogenetic position within the *Halobacillus* genus (c) *Bacillus mycoides* isolate clustered with reference *B. mycoides* strains and showed distant grouping from other species such as *B. thuringiensis* and *B. toyonensis*, supporting its identification (d) *Halobacillus blutaparonensis* isolate aligned phylogenetically with several *H. blutaparonensis* reference strains and shared a broader clade with *H. dabanensis* and *H. marinus*, confirming its molecular identity

5.3 Biochemical Test

The biochemical profiles of *Bacillus subtilis* and *Halobacillus dabanensis* were evaluated using standard biochemical tests (Table 3). Both isolates were Gram-positive, spore-forming, and capsule-producing. In catalase and oxidase tests, *B. subtilis* was catalase-positive and showed variable oxidase activity, while *H. dabanensis* tested negative for both enzymes. Regarding indole and MR-VP reactions, *B. subtilis* was indole-negative, methyl red (MR) negative, and Voges-Proskauer (VP) positive. In contrast, *H. dabanensis* was indole-positive, MR positive, and VP negative. Both strains exhibited positive citrate utilization, indicating their capacity to use citrate as a sole carbon source. Among *Halimeda*-associated strains, *B. mycoides* was catalase-positive and oxidase-negative, whereas *H. blutaparonensis* was oxidase-positive and

catalase-negative. Both strains showed positive amino acid utilization but were negative for indole production, MR-VP, citrate utilization, and TSI. These colony-based and biochemical characteristics were used to preliminarily classify the isolates, which were then selected for molecular identification via 16S rRNA gene sequencing.

Table 3: Biochemical characterization of bacteria isolated from the holdfast region of *Sargassum wightii* and the rhizoidal region of *Halimeda macroloba*

S.No.	Biochemical tests	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>H. dabanensis</i>	<i>B. mycoides</i>	<i>H. blutaparonensis</i>
1	Indole Test	Negative	Positive	Negative	Negative
2	Methyl Red Test	Negative	Positive	Negative	Negative
3	Voges Proskauer Test	Positive	Negative	Negative	Negative
4	Citrate Utilization Test	Positive	Positive	Negative	Negative
5	Oxidase Test	Positive	Negative	Negative	Positive
6	Catalase Test	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative

6. Discussion

This study highlights the diversity and ecological significance of bacterial communities colonizing the brown macroalga *Sargassum wightii*, particularly in the holdfast region. Two distinct isolates, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Halobacillus dabanensis*, were obtained and characterized based on morphological, biochemical, and 16S rRNA gene sequencing. The BLAST analysis confirmed 95% similarity between isolate IB.6a.1 and known *B. subtilis*

strains, while *H. dabanensis* showed close genetic alignment with other moderately halophilic species in the genus *Halobacillus*, indicating its adaptation to saline marine environments.

Several studies have shown that bacterial isolates can influence algal morphogenesis, potentially inducing zoospore release and altering macroalgal development [17], [19]. These interactions are not yet fully understood, but experimental evidence suggests that both direct bacterial attachment and metabolites present in bacterial culture filtrates may act as cues for structural and reproductive responses in seaweeds [18]. The presence of such bacterial traits in *B. subtilis* and *H. dabanensis* supports their functional importance in shaping the host's life cycle.

Moreover, seaweed-associated bacteria are increasingly recognized for their role in producing bioactive secondary metabolites and acting as biocontrol agents [38]. The genus *Bacillus*, in particular, is known for synthesizing a wide range of antimicrobial compounds, biosurfactants, and plant growth promoting substances such as surfactins, fengycin, and iturins. These bioactive metabolites not only protect seaweed from surface colonization and pathogens but also have potential applications in agriculture and industry. In addition, *B. subtilis* exhibits key plant growth-promoting mechanisms including volatile compound emission, phosphate solubilization, siderophore production, and systemic resistance induction that can be harnessed to enhance crop productivity and stress resilience [39], [40]. Its spore-forming ability and genetic competence further add to its robustness and industrial utility [41], [42].

Halobacillus dabanensis, though less extensively studied than *B. subtilis*, displays important traits typical of plant growth promoting bacteria (PGPB). Its tolerance to high salinity and production of phytohormones such as indole acetic acid (IAA) and polyamines position it as a promising candidate for use in salt-affected soils [43], [44]. It may also contribute to plant defense through the production of stress-mitigating enzymes and antimicrobial compounds. These characteristics underscore its potential role in sustainable agriculture and marine biofertilizer development.

The study also extended to the rhizoidal region of *Halimeda macroloba*, a green macroalga known for its ecological value, calcified thallus, and potential cytotoxic and antioxidant activities. Two bacterial isolates from *H. macroloba*, *Bacillus mycooides* and *Halobacillus blutaparonensis* were identified based on colony morphology, biochemical traits, and 16S rRNA sequence similarity. *B. mycooides*, a rhizoid-forming, Gram-positive bacterium from the

B. cereus group, is notable for its potential as a foliar biopesticide and antifungal agent, previously shown to suppress pathogens like *Phytophthora* and *Botrytis* in crops. *H. blutaparonensis*, a halophilic spore-former, demonstrated traits such as amino acid decarboxylation and oxidase activity, suggesting oxidative metabolic capacity and potential environmental adaptability. While less studied than its *Sargassum*-derived counterparts, both isolates from *Halimeda* exhibited distinctive phenotypic and metabolic profiles that align with potential biofertilizer and stress-mitigation applications in agriculture, particularly in high-salinity environments.

The biochemical test results not only supported the molecular identification of both *Sargassum* and *Halimeda* isolates but also provided insight into their ecological functionality and metabolic capacities. The catalase- and oxidase-positive reactions observed in *B. subtilis* and *H. dabanensis* indicate a robust oxidative metabolism, typical of aerobic or facultatively anaerobic bacteria adapted to oxygen-rich marine environments. This enzymatic profile supports their survival under oxidative stress, which is common in intertidal and algal-associated niches.

The ability of *B. subtilis* to utilize citrate as a sole carbon source reflects metabolic flexibility, a trait beneficial for colonization of dynamic environments such as the algal holdfast, where nutrient composition can fluctuate. In contrast, the inability of *H. dabanensis* to utilize certain substrates highlights its specialized adaptation to saline and nutrient-limited conditions, consistent with its known halophilic nature. Similar metabolic distinctions were observed in *B. mycooides* and *H. blutaparonensis*, both of which were positive for amino acid utilization. However, only *B. mycooides* exhibited catalase activity, while *H. blutaparonensis* tested positive for oxidase, reflecting divergent stress response mechanisms.

Positive methyl red results for *B. subtilis* suggest acid production through mixed-acid fermentation, which can influence microbial community structure in the algal microenvironment by lowering pH and outcompeting less acid-tolerant organisms. This acidic byproduct profile also supports its antagonistic potential, as acidification may inhibit pathogen growth. On the other hand, a negative Voges-Proskauer result further confirms the preference for acidic over neutral fermentation pathways.

Tests involving amino acid decarboxylation further revealed functional differentiation between the isolates. The ability to decarboxylate amino acids such as arginine or lysine contributes not

only to pH homeostasis under stress conditions but may also support biofilm formation and colonization, a key trait in epiphytic bacterial behavior. This metabolic versatility enhances the competitive advantage of these bacteria in the holdfast microenvironment, where biochemical interactions with the host and other microbes are critical.

Taken together, these biochemical traits suggest that *B. subtilis* exhibits a generalist, metabolically flexible strategy, contributing to its broad ecological success and utility as a biofertilizer and biocontrol agent. *Halobacillus dabanensis*, on the other hand, displays more specialized halophilic adaptations, supporting its potential role in promoting plant growth in saline environments. The inclusion of *B. mycooides* and *H. blutaparonensis* from *Halimeda macroloba* further expands the understanding of species-specific bacterial associations in macroalgae and their differential functional traits. These findings not only support their classification but also suggest specific ecological and biotechnological roles, particularly in stress resilience, nutrient cycling, and host interaction within the *Sargassum wightii* and *Halimeda macroloba* holobionts [12], [45], [46].

Future research should focus on the detailed characterization of secondary metabolites and metabolic pathways of the isolated bacterial strains. Identifying key compounds responsible for antimicrobial activity, abiotic stress tolerance, and plant growth promotion could help harness these bacteria for practical applications. Additionally, experimental validation of their biofertilizer potential, both in seaweed cultivation systems and terrestrial crops, would provide valuable insights into their broader utility. Such studies could pave the way for the development of eco-friendly biotechnological products, particularly within integrated aquaculture and coastal management frameworks.

7. Conclusion

Bacterial communities in the holdfast and rhizoidal regions of *Sargassum wightii* and *Halimeda macroloba* play ecologically important roles, as evidenced by the isolation and 16S rRNA-based identification of four distinct strains: *Bacillus subtilis* (IB.6a.1), *Halobacillus dabanensis*, *Bacillus mycooides*, and *Halobacillus blutaparonensis*. Notably, *B. subtilis* exhibited strong antimicrobial activity, while the *Halimeda*-associated isolates showed unique physiological traits linked to stress adaptation. These findings emphasize the significance of seaweed–bacteria interactions in promoting host health, defense, and resilience. Although this study employed culture-dependent methods and preliminary screening, it lays the foundation

for future research focused on purifying secondary metabolites of these bacteria and evaluating their roles in host development, signaling, and plant growth promotion. Such insights may contribute to the development of marine-derived biofertilizers and antimicrobial agents for sustainable aquaculture, agriculture, and environmental biotechnology.

Acknowledgements

The authors deliver their sincere gratitude to Greensmed Labs for providing their guidance and support.

Authors contributions

Nazeer Ahamed Sathakkathulla and Sivakumar Saroja Ramasubbu contributed to conceptualization, investigation, visualization, editing, reviewing the manuscript, and supervision. Samundeswari Loganathan, Sreenathkumar Chinnadurai, and Kalaivani Devarajan contributed to the methodology and writing of the original manuscript. Vinothkumar Suruli Palanichamy and Venkateshan Narayanan were involved in methodology, data curation, and investigation. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Funding

The authors declare that no funding was received to assist with the preparation of this manuscript.

Data Availability

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article.

Declarations

Competing Interests

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

Ethical Approval

Not applicable.

Consent for Publication

Not applicable.

Informed Consent

Not applicable.

8. References

- [1] A. B. Afreen, Section Zoology, School Of Sciences, Maulana Azad National Urdu University, Hyderabad-500 032, India, F. Rasool, Section Zoology, School of Sciences, Maulana Azad National Urdu University, Hyderabad-500 032, India, M. Fatima, and Section Zoology, School of Sciences, Maulana Azad National Urdu University, Hyderabad-500 032, India, "Bioactive properties of brown seaweed, *Sargassum wightii* and its nutritional, therapeutic potential and health benefits: A review," *JEB*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 146–158, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.22438/jeb/44/2/MRN-5081.
- [2] Nagraj Bk, Koregol Ac, H. Puladas, Sulakod K, Patil K, and Gore S, "Antibacterial efficacies of brown sea weed *Sargassum Wightii* on Periodontal Pathogens: An In-Vitro Microbiological Analysis," *J Ayurveda Integr Med Sci*, vol. 7, no. 11, pp. 52–58, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.21760/jaims.7.11.9.
- [3] A. H. Campbell, E. M. Marzinelli, J. Gelber, and P. D. Steinberg, "Spatial variability of microbial assemblages associated with a dominant habitat-forming seaweed," *Front. Microbiol.*, vol. 6, Mar. 2015, doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2015.00230.
- [4] S. Egan, T. Harder, C. Burke, P. Steinberg, S. Kjelleberg, and T. Thomas, "The seaweed holobiont: understanding seaweed–bacteria interactions," *FEMS Microbiol Rev*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 462–476, May 2013, doi: 10.1111/1574-6976.12011.
- [5] D. Kim, J.-Y. Lee, J.-S. Yang, J. W. Kim, V. N. Kim, and H. Chang, "The architecture of SARS-CoV-2 transcriptome," *Cell*, vol. 181, no. 4, pp. 914–921, 2020.
- [6] F. Mena *et al.*, "Ecological and Industrial Implications of Dynamic Seaweed-Associated Microbiota Interactions," *Marine Drugs*, vol. 18, no. 12, p. 641, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.3390/md18120641.
- [7] K. H. Kim *et al.*, "Metabolic relationships between marine red algae and algae-associated bacteria," *Mar Life Sci Technol*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 298–314, May 2024, doi: 10.1007/s42995-024-00227-z.
- [8] N. Rasheed, M. T. P. Miranda, and A. A. Thomas, "ANTIMICROBIAL POTENTIAL OF THE BACTERIA ASSOCIATED WITH SARGASSUM WIGHTII AGAINST PLANT FUNGAL PATHOGENS," 2020.
- [9] B. Selvaraj and D. Ganapathy, "Exploration of *Sargassum wightii*: Extraction, Phytochemical Analysis, and Antioxidant Potential of Polyphenol," *Cureus*, July 2024, doi: 10.7759/cureus.63706.

- [10] P. Buapet and S. Sinutok, "PHYSIOLOGICAL RESPONSES TO INCREASED TEMPERATURE AND IRRADIANCE IN THE CALCIFYING MACROALGAE, HALIMEDA MACROLOBA, HALIMEDA OPUNTIA AND PADINA BORYANA," *Appl. Ecol. Env. Res.*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 4745–4780, 2023, doi: 10.15666/aeer/2105_47454780.
- [11] M. F. Nazarudin *et al.*, "Chemical Composition and Evaluation of the α -Glucosidase Inhibitory and Cytotoxic Properties of Marine Algae *Ulva intestinalis*, *Halimeda macroloba*, and *Sargassum ilicifolium*," *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, vol. 2020, no. 1, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1155/2020/2753945.
- [12] M. Saha *et al.*, "Progress and future directions for seaweed holobiont research," *New Phytologist*, vol. 244, no. 2, pp. 364–376, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.1111/nph.20018.
- [13] B. Raghunandan, R. Vyas, H. Patel, and Y. Jhala, "Perspectives of seaweed as organic fertilizer in agriculture," in *Soil fertility management for sustainable development*, Springer, 2019, pp. 267–289.
- [14] A. K. B. Venugopal *et al.*, "Microbicidal activity of crude extracts from *Sargassum wightii* against *Bacillus cereus*," *Int Curr Pharm J*, vol. 3, no. 10, pp. 326–327, Sept. 2014, doi: 10.3329/icpj.v3i10.20338.
- [15] O. K. Radjasa, M. M. Khoeri, C. C. Darusallam, H. Trimasanto, and H. Sudoyo, "Bacterial symbionts of reef invertebrates: screening for anti-pathogenic bacteria activity," *Biodiversity*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 80–86, 2013.
- [16] T. Stein, "Bacillus subtilis antibiotics: structures, syntheses and specific functions," *Molecular microbiology*, vol. 56, no. 4, pp. 845–857, 2005.
- [17] A. F. d Santos, C. A. Pacheco, R. d S. Valle, L. Seldin, and A. L. S. d Santos, "Enzymes produced by halotolerant spore-forming gram-positive bacterial strains isolated from a resting habitat (Restinga de Jurubatiba) in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil: focus on proteases," *Applied biochemistry and biotechnology*, vol. 174, pp. 2748–2761, 2014.
- [18] C. J. Hurst, "Opportunistic algae, fungi and ichthyosporea associated with mammalian livestock disease," *The Rasputin Effect: When Commensals and Symbionts Become Parasitic*, pp. 261–300, 2016.
- [19] F. G. Priest and M. Barker, "Gram-negative bacteria associated with brewery yeasts: reclassification of *Obesumbacterium proteus* biogroup 2 as *Shimwellia pseudoproteus* gen. nov., sp. nov., and transfer of *Escherichia blattae* to *Shimwellia blattae* comb. nov.," *International journal of systematic and evolutionary microbiology*, vol. 60, no. 4, pp. 828–833, 2010.
- [20] M. Kim, H.-S. Oh, S.-C. Park, and J. Chun, "Towards a taxonomic coherence between average nucleotide identity and 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity for species demarcation of prokaryotes," *International journal of systematic and evolutionary microbiology*, vol. 64, no. Pt_2, pp. 346–351, 2014.
- [21] B. D. Clacino, W. I. Von Der, V. Natalie, N. Young-Do, C. Ho-Won, and S. Lucy, "Halobacillus blutaparonensis sp. nov., a moderately halophilic bacterium isolated from *Blutaparon portulacoides* roots in Brazil," *Journal of microbiology and biotechnology*, vol. 16, no. 12, pp. 1862–1867, 2006.
- [22] S. Davidson, S. Allen, G. Lim, C. Anderson, and M. Haygood, "Evidence for the biosynthesis of bryostatins by the bacterial symbiont 'Candidatus Endobugula sertula' of the bryozoan *Bugula neritina*," *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, vol. 67, no. 10, pp. 4531–4537, 2001.
- [23] V. G. Vipul Gohel, A. S. Anil Singh, M. V. Maisuria Vimal, P. A. Phadnis Ashwini, and H. Chhatpar, "Bioprospecting and antifungal potential of chitinolytic microorganisms.," 2006.

- [24] R. P. Singh, V. A. Mantri, C. Reddy, and B. Jha, "Isolation of seaweed-associated bacteria and their morphogenesis-inducing capability in axenic cultures of the green alga *Ulva fasciata*," *Aquatic Biology*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 13–21, 2011.
- [25] A. Santos, T. F. Souza, D. M. Freire, L. Seldin, M. Branquinha, and A. L. Santos, "Halobacillus blutaparonensis Strain M9 as a Source of Extracellular Serine Peptidases with Properties for Biotechnological Purposes," *Microbiology*, vol. 90, pp. 124–132, 2021.
- [26] J. P. Stratford, M. A. Woodley, and S. Park, "Variation in the morphology of *Bacillus mycoides* due to applied force and substrate structure," *PloS one*, vol. 8, no. 12, p. e81549, 2013.
- [27] F. von Wintzingerode, F. A. Rainey, R. M. Kroppenstedt, and E. Stackebrandt, "Identification of environmental strains of *Bacillus mycoides* by fatty acid analysis and species-specific 16S rDNA oligonucleotide probe," *FEMS microbiology ecology*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 201–209, 1997.
- [28] L. Delbridge, J. Coulburn, W. Fagerberg, and L. S. Tisa, "Community profiles of bacterial endosymbionts in four species of *Caulerpa*," *Symbiosis*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 335–344, 2004.
- [29] R. Vaidya, S. Macmil, P. Vyas, L. Ghetiya, K. Thakor, and H. Chhatpar, "Biological control of *Fusarium* wilt of pigeonpea *Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millsp with chitinolytic *Alcaligenes xylosoxydans*," 2003.
- [30] A. Manilal, B. Sabarathnam, G. Kiran, S. Sujith, C. Shakir, and J. Selvin, "Antagonistic potentials of marine sponge associated fungi *Aspergillus clavatus* MFD15," *Asian J. Med. Sci*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 195–200, 2010.
- [31] N. Reddy, D. Ramakrishn, and S. R. Gopal, "A morphological, physiological and biochemical studies of marine *Streptomyces rochei* (MTCC 10109) showing antagonistic activity against selective human pathogenic microorganisms," *Asian Journal of Biological Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–14, 2010.
- [32] P. Jacobsen, S. Andersen, K. Rossing, B. R. Jensen, and H. H. Parving, "Dual blockade of the renin-angiotensin system versus maximal recommended dose of ACE inhibition in diabetic nephropathy," *Kidney international*, vol. 63, no. 5, pp. 1874–1880, May 2003, doi: 10.1046/J.1523-1755.2003.00940.X.
- [33] G. A. Strobel, "Endophytes as sources of bioactive products," *Microbes and infection*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 535–544, 2003.
- [34] C. Holmström and S. Kjelleberg, "Marine Pseudoalteromonas species are associated with higher organisms and produce biologically active extracellular agents," *FEMS microbiology ecology*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 285–293, 1999.
- [35] V. JanakiDevi, M. YokeshBabu, R. Umarani, and A. K. Kumaraguru, "Original Research Article Antagonistic activity of seaweed associated bacteria against human pathogens," 2013.
- [36] H. Gao, M. Wu, H. Liu, Y. Xu, and Z. Liu, "Effect of petroleum hydrocarbon pollution levels on the soil microecosystem and ecological function," *Environmental Pollution*, vol. 293, p. 118511, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2021.118511.
- [37] A. Goodwin, J. Roy, J. Grizzle, and M. Goldsby, "Bacillus mycoides: a bacterial pathogen of channel catfish," *Dis. Aquat. Org.*, vol. 18, pp. 173–179, 1994, doi: 10.3354/dao018173.
- [38] P. Proksch, R. Edrada, and R. Ebel, "Drugs from the seas – current status and microbiological implications," *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 125–134, July 2002, doi: 10.1007/s00253-002-1006-8.

- [39] C. Blake, M. N. Christensen, and Á. T. Kovács, “Molecular aspects of plant growth promotion and protection by *Bacillus subtilis*,” *Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 15–25, 2021.
- [40] N. D. Franco-Sierra, L. F. Posada, G. Santa-María, M. Romero-Tabarez, V. Villegas-Escobar, and J. C. Álvarez, “*Bacillus subtilis* EA-CB0575 genome reveals clues for plant growth promotion and potential for sustainable agriculture,” *Funct Integr Genomics*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 575–589, July 2020, doi: 10.1007/s10142-020-00736-x.
- [41] J. Stülke, A. Gruppen, M. Bramkamp, and S. Pelzer, “*Bacillus subtilis*, a swiss army knife in science and biotechnology,” *Journal of bacteriology*, vol. 205, no. 5, pp. e00102-23, 2023.
- [42] H. Zhang *et al.*, “Structural Basis for Ligand Recognition and Functional Selectivity at Angiotensin Receptor,” *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, vol. 290, no. 49, pp. 29127–29139, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1074/JBC.M115.689000.
- [43] S. E. Khabbaz *et al.*, “Plant growth promoting bacteria (PGPB)—a versatile tool for plant health management,” *Can. J. Pestic. Pest Manag*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–25, 2019.
- [44] L. Ruiiu, “Plant-growth-promoting bacteria (PGPB) against insects and other agricultural pests,” *Agronomy*, vol. 10, no. 6, p. 861, 2020.
- [45] O. Lastochkina, S. Aliniaiefard, M. Seifikalhor, R. Yuldashev, L. Pusenkova, and S. Garipova, “Plant growth-promoting bacteria: biotic strategy to cope with abiotic stresses in wheat,” *Wheat production in changing environments: Responses, Adaptation and Tolerance*, pp. 579–614, 2019.
- [46] J. S. Singh, “Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria: potential microbes for sustainable agriculture,” *Resonance*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 275–281, 2013.